

Patient Body Vitals Monitoring and Alerting System with Raspberry-Pi and Multi channel Wi-Fi Communication

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Abstract

Extensive research is done on present technology on wireless patient monitoring devices .This paper proposes intelligent Wi-Fi enabled wireless device to seamlessly monitor patient vitals and transmit the data continuously to another display device connected to internet .The algorithm proposed is hardwired and fail proof and sensors were so advanced that minute deviation can also be detected and send email to stored mail ids instantly.

Key words: *Raspberry Pi, Wi-Fi Enabled ,Wireless ,Medical , Patient-Monitoring , Blood-Pressure ,Body-Temperature , Human-Vitals , Sensors ,Biomedical-Device .*

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